

A Literature Review of Positive Work Culture in Human Resource Management

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ABSTRACT: Work culture is widely considered to be one of the most important determinants of organizational variables. Every organization has its own unique organizational culture, which reflects the behavior of employees within the organization. The challenge for managers today is managing employees from different cultures, which have a significant impact on workplace behavior, management practices, and organizational effectiveness and efficiency. A review of the literature reveals that studies that have investigated the relationship between work culture and organizational variables vary in their conceptualization. The purpose of this study is to expand the knowledge base about the relationship between work culture and other organizational variables.. Our analysis provides a blueprint to guide future research and facilitates knowledge accumulation and creation concerning the organizational performance impacts of work culture. Research reveals that possession of similar norms and values by the organization and its employees will improve the performance of the organization towards achieving the goals of the organization.

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INTRODUCTION

Work culture is an assumption, values and norms that are carried out repeatedly by employees or employees that are developed within the organization. It reflected in attitudes to behavior, beliefs, ideals, opinions and actions that are manifested as work or work as a force to improve work efficiency. It is a philosophical statement, its function as binding demands on worker; it can be formally formulated in various company rules and regulations. Work culture is a set of behavior patterns that are inherent in every individual in an organization as a whole. Building a culture also means increasing and maintaining positive sides, as well as trying to get used to certain patterns of behavior in order to create a new, better form.

Work culture is individual habit in an organization which belief and value stem from customs, religion, norms and rules. These are called culture and considering this is associated with the quality of work and performance. A workplace culture or Work culture is a collection of attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors that form an orderly atmosphere in a work environment. A healthy workplace culture aligns employee behavior and company policies with overall company goals, while considering individual well-being.

Work culture determines how well a person adjusts to their environment at a new job and their ability to build professional relationships with colleagues. Employee attitude, work-life balance, growth opportunities, and job satisfaction all depend on the culture of a workplace.

Work culture is a complex concept that is constantly evolving in the workplace based on many elements. While some people may appreciate a more traditional work culture and others want something more modern and fun, all healthy work cultures have a lot in common.

According to Mangkunegara (2005), work culture is a set of assumptions or a system of beliefs, values and norms developed within an organization which is used as a guideline for the behavior of its members to overcome problems of external adaptation and internal integration. Triguno (2003), work culture is a philosophy based on a view of life as values that become traits, habits and driving forces, entrenched in the life of a community or organization, then reflected from attitudes into behavior, beliefs, ideals, opinions and actions that manifest as work or work. Further reading, Nawawi (2003), work culture is a habit that is carried out repeatedly by employees in an organization, violations of these habits do not have strict sanctions, but morally organizational

actors have agreed that these habits are habits that must be obeyed in order to execution of work to achieve goals. Ndraha (2003), work culture is a group of basic thoughts or mental programs that can be used to improve work efficiency and human cooperation that belongs to a certain group of people. According to Hartanto (2009), work culture is a manifestation of life found in the workplace. Work culture is a system of meaning related to work interaction, which is mutually agreed upon, and used in daily work life.

TYPES OF WORK CULTURE

According to Tika (2008), there are several types of work culture, namely as follows:

1. Rational culture. In this culture, individual information processes (objective clarification logical considerations, directive tools) are assumed to be the means to the indicated performance goals (efficiency, productivity and profit or impact).
2. Ideological culture. In this culture, intuitive information processing (from deep knowledge, opinion and innovation) is assumed to be a vehicle for revitalization purposes (outside support, resource acquisition and growth).
3. Consensus culture. In this culture, collective information processing (discussion, participation and consensus) is assumed to be a vehicle for cohesion goals (climate, morale and group cooperation).
4. Hierarchical culture. In a hierarchical culture, formal information processing (documentation, computation and evaluation) is assumed to be a vehicle for sustainability goals (stability, control and coordination).

Having a work culture at work creates various benefits and positive impacts. A good work culture can increase work productivity and also make worker feel comfortable at work.

RESEARCH IN WORK CULTURE

Several research have shown that if other variable increased there will be positive effect in work culture. Improving work culture may add value. Work culture is closely related to maintaining employee mentality and can also affect employee performance. This culture is also a determining factor for the success of a company.

Therefore, creating a positive work culture is a must for business owners and their employees. Because this also reflects the values of a company and can have a positive impact.

Miyono and Rosidin (2017), competence and motivation have positive effect on work culture. According to the reaserch,when there is an improvement in any of the variable, work culture will improve. Further research by Ainurrofiq and Amir (2022) confirm that work culture change will make a positive change in the way of communicating and collaborating. Sidauruk, and Gunawan (2021), conclude that leadership has significant effect on work culture. Sembiring and Sofyan (2021) conclude that management style has an effect on work culture. Jamaludin (2019) motivation and work discipline are partially affecting work culture. Simbolon (2017) mentioned that leadership, motivation and competency are positively affecting work culture. Septyaningsih (2021), positive work culture increase work productivity. Arianto (2013) and Kurniawan, et. al. (2012) work culture has positive impact on employee performance. Positive impact means when there is an increase in motivation, work ethic and work efficient would result higher performance.

Research shown work culture has relationship with performance. A good work culture has a positive influence on employee performance. A healthy and positive work culture will create a work environment that motivates employees to work better and effectively. Managers shape the corporate culture of their hiring practices, where they can select applicants whose personal vision aligns with a healthy work culture. The workplace environment also influences culture, with many offices opting for open floor plans, natural lighting, and the inclusion of amenities such as in-office gyms and break room facilities. Work culture is formed and developed naturally over time as a result of previous worker interactions. That is, work culture is not created just like that, but it exists because the company has gone through various problems and learned to overcome them.

People are generally happier, more productive, and more focused when they feel able to express themselves at work. If employees have freedom in their personal style and how they decorate their workspace, it shows a level of comfort in their work culture.

FUNCTIONS AND OBJECTIVES OF WORK CULTURE

According to Feriyanto and Triana (2015), the goals of work culture are as follows:

1. Culture creates a clear distinction between one organization and another.
2. Culture brings a sense of identity to the members of the organization.
3. Culture facilitates the emergence of a commitment to something that is already broader than one's individual self-interest.
4. Culture is the social glue that helps unite the organization by providing proper standards for employees to perform.
5. Culture as a meaning-making and control mechanism that guides and shapes employee attitudes and behavior.

A positive work culture can be formed if employees are involved and implement it in the work environment. To realize this, you must be selective in recruiting new employees. Choose one that really has a brush, nature, and way of working that fits the company culture.

Elements of a healthy work culture

Culture is a complex concept that is constantly evolving in the workplace based on many elements. While some people may appreciate a more traditional work culture and others want something more modern and fun, all healthy work cultures have a lot in common. Look for these signs of a good work culture when considering potential employers.

Accountability

When everyone who works in a company is responsible for his behavior, it indicates a healthy working environment. A balanced workplace allows people to feel comfortable enough to appreciate their ideas and mistakes.

Open accountability allows each employee to learn from challenges rather than avoid them. Accountability fosters a work culture based on teamwork, open communication, trustworthiness and responsibility.

Equity

Companies that treat all their employees equally often have a healthy work culture. Every position in a company has value, and providing opportunities to everyone will increase employee morale. Favoritism in the workplace is a sign of a toxic work culture and can lead to feelings of mistrust and resentment among colleagues, making a fair workplace environment essential for a positive work culture.

Expression

People are generally happier, more productive, and more focused when they feel able to express expression at work. If employees have freedom in their personal style and how they decorate their workspace, it shows a level of comfort in their work culture.

Expression in company culture perspective is about creating an environment that aligns with the organization's values and objectives. Human resource people must be aware of the culture's impact on every aspect of employees' experiences, starting from recruitment to performance management, then work actively to ensure that policies, practices, and initiatives support a positive and productive workplace culture.

Communication

Open communication is essential for a productive workplace environment. Everyone in a company must understand how to give and receive feedback, share ideas, collaborate, and solve problems.

All teams have interpersonal conflicts sometimes, but a functional work culture will allow them to solve problems and work as a team despite challenges. Avoid companies with work cultures where people feel unable to talk about conflicts or concerns, as there won't be much room for growth.

Confession

A thriving work culture recognizes employee success and rewards people when they do well. Management in a healthy workplace environment will look for positive attributes from everyone on the team and encourage the use of their talents. Employee recognition ranging from regular verbal praise to competitive pay can build a work culture that values and respects each other.

Productive work environment

One of the characteristics of a company that has a positive work culture is its productive work environment. All the workers in it feel happy and enjoy the work they do. A productive work environment based in a supportive and empowering company culture can significantly impact employee performance. By fostering clear communication, trust, recognition, and professional development, organizations can create an environment where employees thrive and productivity accompaniments. As companies continuously evolve, they must regularly assess and adapt their culture to maintain this productive environment, ensuring they meet both organizational goals and employee needs

Pleasant working atmosphere

Many workers feel stressed at work because the office atmosphere is not conducive and tends to be rigid. Well, companies with a positive work culture usually free employees to occasionally interact and laugh with their coworkers while working. This kind of work culture will make employees more relaxed, less stressed, and comfortable to work.

Open and candid communication

In addition to the working atmosphere, open and honest communication or what it is is also one of the characteristics of a company with a positive work culture. Imagine if employees can communicate honestly, are open to opinions and feedback from others, and work together in solving problems, it will certainly create a positive work culture.

Reward and motivation

Of course, it is a pleasant thing for employees when they have succeeded in achieving the target and the given awards for them in the form of bonuses, promotions, certificates. That way, employees will feel valued and more motivated to contribute to the company.

Good cooperation

Every employee will definitely get tasks that require to cooperate with other employees. A good work culture will encourage employees to work well together and compete healthily. Thus, the results of the work obtained become more optimal and have a positive impact on the development of the company.

CONCLUSION

We have studied the literature and describe the relation amongst work culture and other organizational variables. The primary contribution of this review is the model which shows the present state of knowledge on Culture in the literature. This lets the future researchers of work culture to broaden them within a cumulative practice that has rich knowledge to offer. The set of propositions which the firms can use to predict the results of a development process is the contribution of this review to practitioners. Besides this review also shows the actions and strategies which can be taken to ease the adverse effects of work cultural differences in the firms.

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